

Amihan's Breath: Development of an IoT-Integrated Arduino System for Real-Time Indoor Air Quality Monitoring, Alert Notification, and Filtration

Jaydonn Arvin H. Santillana, Jay Laurence L. Quimque, John M. Pagaran, Benjo R. Saraka, Joseph Ramos, Jaine D. Luz

Carlos P. Garcia Senior High School (CPGSHS), Davao City, Davao Del Sur.

Abstract- This study describes Amihan's Breath, an Internet-of-Things-based air quality management system using Arduino R4 Wi-Fi that monitors and regulates indoor air quality (IAQ) in Davao City. The system measures 12 air quality and thermal parameters, including PM1.0, PM2.5, PM10, NOx, CO, O₃, NH₃, VOCs, temperature, and humidity, and provides real-time monitoring, alerts, and air-filtering functions. Sensor accuracy ranged from 97–100% before and after filtration. Initial IAQ analysis indicated moderate pollution levels, with PM10 averaging 85.64 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ and NOx averaging 96.89 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$. After filtration, pollutant levels significantly decreased, including a 29% reduction in NOx and substantial reductions in particulate matter. Overall, Amihan's Breath is an effective and cost-efficient IAQ management system recommended for high-risk environments such as schools and healthcare facilities.

Keywords – Indoor Air Quality (IAQ), Arduino-Based Monitoring System, Indoor Air Quality (IAQ), Air Filtration, Particulate Matter, Arduino R4 Wi-Fi, Internet of Things (IoT).

I. INTRODUCTION

Air pollution is the harmful contamination of the atmosphere from pollutants released from many different sources, such as industries, vehicles, and natural sources. Air pollution is an environmental hazard, with damaging effects on human health, including respiratory diseases and other health issues. Air pollution also contaminates ecological systems and exacerbates climate change. In Davao City, air pollution is especially aggravated by local sources of pollution, such as cooking and tobacco smoke, products used in the home, and from the interception of further external sources such as outdoor air pollution and smoke from fires. Exposure to indoor air pollution without treatment can disrupt health and lead to significant health impacts, including respiratory illnesses, cardiovascular disease, stroke, lung cancer, migraines, dizziness, fatigue and increased risk of infections. Indoor air pollution can worsen asthma and other chronic diseases. Vulnerable people such as children, the elderly, and pregnant women can experience increased incidence of these conditions, and this results in millions of premature deaths globally every year (United States Environmental Protection Agency, 2025). These conditions collectively underscored the necessity for protecting indoor air quality to safeguard the health of both the human and indoor environment.

Liu et al. (2021), indoor air quality was studied in 66 primary school classrooms at 22 schools in China. Of the classrooms

measured, 66.5% exceeded Particulate Matter 2.5 limit values, 52.6% exceeded Particulate Matter 10 limit values, and 22.4% exceeded Carbon Dioxide limits. Each of these pollutants poses a health risk to students, who are inherently at risk for health problems when exposed, including airway and respiratory conditions, decreased lung function, and other health issues. The exposures that millions of student experience create a public health challenge in addition to threatening academic performance. Additionally, indoor air pollution as a result of cooking with solid fuels affects approximately 2.1 billion people worldwide, mainly in low- and middle-income countries, and causes around 3.2 million premature deaths each year, including 237.00 children under five years old (World Health Organization, 2024).

Statement of the Problem

This study aimed to create and deploy "Amihan's Breath", an automated IoT-Integrated Arduino System for real-time indoor air quality monitoring, alert notification, and filtration in Davao City. The system allowed the monitoring, alert notification, and air purification of important environmental information, enabling the detection and assessment of indoor air quality to create a healthier indoor environment.

II. METHODS

This chapter presents the study method, which include four (4) phases: Phase 1 - Designing of the IoT-Integrated Arduino

System for real-time indoor air quality monitoring, alert notification, and filtration: Amihan's Breath (Mechanical and Structural Frame Design); Phase II – Testing indicators; Phase III – Data Collection; Phase IV – Data Analysis. All of the tests and experimental procedures were conducted at Carlos P. Garcia Senior High School.

Research Design

The study used experimental approach to test the operational efficiency and reliability of the Amihan's Breath system. The phase to the design includes the development of the prototype followed by field pilot testing, then controlled testing, and so forth. Throughout a period of time that was designated for testing, the accuracy of the sensors, performance of the system, and transmission of the data was measured and monitored to determine reliability, responsiveness, and usability of the device for real-time indoor air quality monitoring.

Phase I. Designing of the Arduino (IoT) Based Real-time Indoor Air Quality Monitoring, Alert Notification, and Filtration System: Amihan's Breath Prototype

Materials. The prototype consisted of 15 materials containing the Arduino Uno R4 Wi-Fi, 12 V Uninterruptible Power Supply, PMS7003, MQ131, MQ7, MIC5524, DHT22, DC-DC Buck Converter, 12V Blower Fan, Buzzer, LED, OLED, Servo Motor, Wires, and 3D Printed Structure.

System Design

After considering several ideas while choosing an appropriate system. Upon a thorough analysis, they chose to research a topic concerning solving the problem of air quality, Amihan's Breath. This system is meant to address some of the problems that are usually experienced by most people, especially nowadays.

To build the system, the researchers conducted extensive online research, reading related articles to determine the system requirements and specifications that would be required to solve the issues encountered. The team used microcontrollers like Arduino and combined it with other sensors, to learn how they work and choose the most applicable components.

Figure 1 illustrates the system design prepared for the study. In order to meet the engineering objectives, the researchers need to first set up and interconnect all the components of the system that are necessary. The Arduino R4 wi-fi serves as the microcontroller; it receives data, executes instructions, and commands the actions of the other components that take part in the design.

Figure 1. System Design

It also serves as a medium for the ESP32 Wi-Fi Module built-in in it to utilize its time monitoring feature. The input devices for this system are PMS7003, MQ131, MQ7, MIC5524, and DHT22. On the other hand, the output devices for this system will be the 12V Fan Blower, RTC module, MG996R Servo Motor and 12 V Uninterruptible Power Supply.

Circuit Diagram

Figure 2 shows the circuit diagram of the Arduino (IoT) based real-time indoor air quality monitoring, alert notification, and filtration system prototype. The system was programmed using Arduino IDE software. The Arduino microcontroller reads the air pollutants level. If the level exceeds, it will send an alert to notify the premises using the website that it is not safe to inhale the air without a mask. The system will then recheck the air quality regularly to see if it is good or bad.

Figure 2. Circuit Diagram

System Flowchart

Presented in Figure 3 is the flowchart of an Arduino (IoT) based real-time indoor air quality monitoring, alert notification and filtration system. The system was tested after the coding and implementation were done to identify problems. The prototype was placed using a miniature set-up to test whether the concept and wiring worked. Next, an initial placement of the system was conducted. Functionality testing and usability testing was done to complete this study. In all aspects of functional requirements, the developed system should be passed all test cases.

Figure 3. System Flowchart

Device Design

Presented in Figure 4 is the device design of the Arduino (IoT) based real-time indoor air quality monitoring, alert notification, and filtration system for monitoring the air quality in a specific location inside a premises. The Arduino (IoT) based real-time indoor air quality monitoring, alert notification, and filtration system were done after preparation, assembling, and then building a miniature. Materials are considered after searching and browsing the internet for the most appropriate and widely used materials in air quality monitoring.

Figure 4. Device Design

Phase II. Testing Indicators

Presented in Figure 5 is the schematic diagram of the Arduino (IoT) based real-time indoor air quality monitoring, alert notification, and filtration system prototype. The Arduino (IoT) based real-time indoor air quality monitoring, alert notification, and filtration system was tested using the miniature device with alternative chemicals for air pollutants; the sensors were tested to simplify the debugging process. Once it was determined that the sensors were fully functional and performed as foreseen, the next sensor was selected for testing.

Figure 5. Schematic Design

Input and Output Connection

It showed below the type, input, output, pin type, and pin to MCU (Microcontroller) used in the device to simplify the debugging process and easily differentiate the pins used.

Table 1 Input and Output Connection

Component	Type	In/Out	Signal/Pin Type	Pin to MCU
DHT22	Sensor	Input	Digital	D4
PMS7003	Sensor	Input	UART (Serial)	D3 (RX), D2 (TX)
MQ131	Sensor	Input	Analog	A1
MQ7	Sensor	Input	Analog	A0
MICS5524	Sensor	Input	Analog	A3

Formatted Table

12V Fan Blower	Actuator	Output	Power	Not directly to MCU
12V UPS	Power Source	Output	Power	Not directly to MCU
DC Buck Converter	Voltage Regulator	Output	Power	Not directly to MCU
Buzzer	Audio Indicator	Output	Digital	D9
MG996R	Mechanical Output	Output	Digital	D8
RTC	Time Keeping	Input	Analog	SDA=A4, SCL=A5
RGB LED	User Interface	Output	Digital	R=D6, G=D9, B=D10
LED	User Interface	Output	Digital	D12
OLED	User Interface	Output	Analog	SDA=A4, SCL=A5

Detecting Levels of Air Pollutants, Humidity, and Temperature.

The system utilized sensors to monitor atmospheric conditions and air pollutant levels. The DHT22 sensor measured ambient humidity and temperature, while the MQ131, MQ7, MiCS-5524, and PMS7003 sensors detected various air pollutants including Ozone (O₃), Nitrogen Oxides (NO_x), Particulate Matter 1.0 (PM_{1.0}), Particulate Matter 2.5 (PM_{2.5}), Particulate Matter 10 (PM₁₀), Carbon Monoxide (CO), Ammonia (NH₃), and BTX compounds (benzene, toluene, xylene) respectively. These sensors were interfaced with an Arduino UNO R4 Wi-Fi microcontroller, which was programmed using the Arduino IDE.

All of the sensors have digital and analog outputs corresponding to concentrations measured. For instance, the PMS7003 gave real-time PM_{2.5} readings using UART, and the MQ131, MQ7 and MiCS-5524 gave analog voltages that were proportionally related to the levels of ozone and nitrogen dioxide. The higher the output value for each sensor, the higher the concentration of the respective pollutant. Likewise, the DHT22 output values represent the relative humidity and ambient temperature. These readings were computed and recorded, and in case threshold levels were breached, the system sent an alert via the IoT module to inform surrounding users.

Phase III. Data Collection

The data for this research is collected from the testing and operation of the Indoor Air Quality Monitoring, Alert Notification, and Filtration device using Arduino UNO R4 Wi-Fi under real-life or simulated conditions. The prototype was placed in a miniature setup to test the overall functionality of the device. Next, an initial placement of the system was conducted. Functionality and practicality testing were done to

complete this study. In all aspects of functional requirements, the developed system passed all the tests.

Phase IV. Data Analysis

The following statistical tests were used to analyze the data:

Percentage. This was used to determine the successful trials that the Arduino-Based Real-Time Indoor Air Quality Monitoring, Alert Notification, and Filtration system can perform according to the following indicators: Ozone (O₃), Nitrogen Oxides (NO_x), Particulate Matter 1.0 (PM_{1.0}), Particulate Matter 2.5 (PM_{2.5}), Particulate Matter 10 (PM₁₀), Carbon Monoxide (CO), Ammonia (NH₃), and BTX compounds (benzene, toluene, xylene) sensors' detection capabilities; functionality of the Piezo buzzer for alert notifications; and consistency of the system in displaying and transmitting data.

Mean (Average). This was used to determine the average value recorded by the Arduino-Based Real-Time Indoor Air Quality Monitoring, Alert Notification, and Filtration system in terms of PM_{1.0}, PM_{2.5}, PM₁₀, O₃, CO, VOCs, NO_x, NH₃, and BTX levels. This was also used to determine the average readings of temperature and humidity recorded during the operation of the device.

Paired T-test of dependent Means. This was utilized to assess the significant difference in pollutant values before and after implementation of the Arduino-based Real-Time Indoor Air Quality, Alert notification, and Filtration system.

III. RESULTS

This section presents the findings and discussion based on the data gathered. The presentation is organized into four sections: 1) functional accuracy before and after integrating the filtration of the Amihan's Breath; 2) notification accuracy before and after integrating the filtration of the Amihan's Breath System;

3) analog value recorded before and after integrating the filtration by the Amihan's Breath System; and 4) filtration performance of the Amihan's Breath.

Functional Accuracy Before and After of the Amihan's Breath System

Presented in Table 1.1 is the functional accuracy before integrating the filtration of Amihan's Breath when detecting and gathering the data in a dining room, in terms of air pollutants and thermal environment sensors, receiving data on the IoT website based on the data value the system gives, and system programming.

Table 1.1 Functional Accuracy Before Integrating the Filtration

Parameters	Day							Percentage of Success
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	
Air Pollutants								
Ozone (O3)			✓		✓	✓	✓	97%
NOx	✓		✓	✓		✓	✓	98%
Ammonia		✓		✓	✓	✓	✓	99%
Benzene		✓		✓	✓	✓	✓	99%
Toluene		✓		✓	✓	✓	✓	99%
Xylene		✓		✓	✓	✓	✓	99%
PM 1.0			✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	99%
PM 2.5			✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	99%
PM 10			✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	99%
CO		✓			✓	✓	✓	97%
Thermal Environment								
Temperature	✓	✓		✓	✓	✓	✓	99%
Humidity	✓	✓		✓	✓	✓	✓	99%

It shows that the Amihan's Breath system prototype successfully performed ranging 97 to 99 percent within the 7 days of monitoring and detecting air pollutants and thermal environment sensors before integrating the filtration.

Moreover, the consistently high functional accuracy observed across all twelve (12) parameters (97% to 99) fundamentally capable of making precise and reliable measurements of both air pollutants (O3, NOx, CO, Ammonia, Benzene, Toluene,

Xylene, Particulate Matter) and thermal environment (Temperature and Humidity).

Presented in Table 1.2 is the functional accuracy after integrating the filtration of Amihan's Breath when detecting and gathering the data in a dining room, in terms of air pollutants and thermal environment sensors, receiving data on the IoT website based on the data value the system gives, and system programming.

Table 1.2 Functional Accuracy After Integrating the Filtration

Parameters	Day							Percentage of Success
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	
Air Pollutants								
Ozone (O3)	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	100%
NOx	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	100%
Ammonia		✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	99%
Benzene		✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	99%
Toluene		✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	99%
Xylene		✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	99%
PM 1.0	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	100%
PM 2.5	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	100%
PM 10	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	100%
CO	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	100%
Thermal Environment								

Temperature	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	100%
Humidity	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	100%

It shows that the Amihan's Breath system prototype successfully performed ranging 99 to 100 percent within another 7 days of monitoring and detecting air pollutants and thermal environment sensors after integrating the filtration. Furthermore, the functional accuracy after integrating the filtration showed a significant improvement in overall stability and precision. The system demonstrated near-perfect measurement capability, achieving 100 percent accuracy for six

Notification Accuracy Before and After Integrating the Filtration of Amihan's Breath Presented in Table 2.1 is the notification accuracy before and after integrating the filtration of Amihan's Breath when detecting and gathering the data in a dining room, in terms of air pollutants and thermal environment sensors, receiving data on the IoT website based on the data value the system gives, and system programming.

Parameters	Day														Percentage of Success	
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14		
Air Pollutants																
Ozone (O3)	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	100%
NOx	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	100%
Ammonia	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	100%
Benzene	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	100%
Toluene	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	100%
Xylene	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	100%
PM 1.0	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	99%
PM 2.5	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	100%
PM 10	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	99%
CO	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	100%
Thermal Environment																
Temperature	✓	✓		✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	99%
Humidity	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	100%

parameters.

Table 2.1 Notification Accuracy Before and After Integrating the Filtration

Analog Value Recorded on the IoT by the Amihan's Breath Before and After Integrating the Filtration

System in terms of air pollutants and thermal environment during the first seven (7) days monitoring.

Presented 3.1 is the analog value recorded before integrating the filtration on the IoT by the Amihan's Breath

Table 3.1 Analog Value Recorded Before Integration of Filtration

Parameters	Range	Days							Mean
		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	
Air Pollutants									
Ozone (O3)	≤0.06 - 0.07 ppm EMB, 2016)	0.02	0.02	0.03	0.03	0.03	0.03	0.03	0.03
NOx	0-150 µg/m ³ (EMB, 2016)	63.11	88.05	82.53	94.61	100.41	119.08	130.43	96.89

Ammonia	0.5-1.0 ppm (Briones et al., 2019)	0.09	0.6	0.64	0.56	0.86	0.71	0.70	0.59
Benzene	0-10 ppb (DLSU, 2019)	1.02	5.46	2.52	2.41	4.91	3.88	3.48	3.38
Toluene	0-50 ppb (DLSU, 2019)	4.82	16.63	21.30	5.95	20.38	17.71	18.04	14.97
Xylene	0-50 ppb (DLSU, 2019)	4.82	16.63	21.30	5.95	20.38	17.71	18.04	14.97
PM 1.0	< 10-20 µg/m ³ (DLSU, 2019)	15.62	18.59	17.83	19.08	18.63	18.58	18.25	18.08
PM 2.5	≤ 35 µg/m ³ (EMB, 2013)	20.48	30.78	29.43	29.88	31.96	30.33	39.29	30.31
PM 10	≤ 54-150 µg/m ³ (EMB, 2016)	41.19	70.41	96.78	92.67	99.04	114.63	84.79	85.64
CO	≤ 9-15 ppm (EMB, 2016)	10.47	9.77	9.22	9.03	9.89	8.90	9.10	9.48
Thermal environment									
Temperature	20°C to 30°C (DLSU, 2019)	23.19	25.04	23.52	23.46	22.46	23.25	23.25	23.45
Humidity	40% to 60% (DLSU, 2019)	51.05	46.83	50.17	50.29	50.54	49.96	50.21	49.87

It implies that the analog value before integrating the filtration during the first seven (7) days of monitoring are exceeding on the good to moderate threshold levels, such as Particulate Matter 1.0 (PM1.0), Particulate Matter 10 (PM10), and Carbon Monoxide (CO). It shows that the IoT in the Amihan's Breath System consistently recorded the air pollutants and thermal environment.

Presented 3.2 is the analog value recorded after integrating the filtration on the IoT by the Amihan's Breath System in terms of air pollutants and thermal environment during the second seven (7) days monitoring.

Table 3.2 Analog Value Recorded After Integration of Filtration

Parameters	Range	Day							Mean
		8	9	10	11	12	13	14	
Air Pollutants									
Ozone (O ₃)	≤0.06 - 0.07 ppm EMB, 2016)	0.02	0.02	0.02	0.02	0.02	0.02	0.01	0.02
NO _x	0-150 µg/m ³ (EMB, 2016)	72.52	71.62	71.03	70.35	66.70	66.47	63.76	68.92
Ammonia	0.5-1.0 ppm (Briones et al., 2019)	0.55	0.54	0.54	0.54	0.52	0.52	0.50	0.53
Benzene	0-10 ppb (DLSU, 2019)	1.25	1.19	1.16	1.14	0.91	0.94	0.74	1.05
Toluene	0-50 ppb (DLSU, 2019)	6.75	6.17	5.83	5.67	4.13	4.08	3.71	5.19
Xylene	0-50 ppb (DLSU, 2019)	6.75	6.17	5.83	5.67	4.13	4.08	3.71	5.19
PM 1.0	< 10-20 µg/m ³ (DLSU, 2019)	5.92	5.58	5.54	5.92	4.04	3.88	2.54	4.77
PM 2.5	≤ 35 µg/m ³ (EMB, 2013)	7.54	7.29	7.17	6.92	5.21	4.92	3.46	6.07
PM 10	≤ 54-150 µg/m ³ (EMB, 2016)	9.83	9.58	9.42	8.83	7.5	7.12	5.42	8.24
CO	≤ 9-15 ppm (EMB, 2016)	3.51	3.50	3.39	2.72	2.70	2.58	2.36	2.97
Thermal environment									
Temperature	20°C to 30°C (DLSU, 2019)	24.42	24.29	24.96	24.92	24.46	24.79	23.88	24.53
Humidity	40% to 60% (DLSU, 2019)	52.67	52.75	51.75	52.38	50.92	51.04	49.92	51.63

It signifies that the analog value after integrating the filtration during the second seven (7) days of monitoring are substantially decreased on the good to moderate threshold levels, such as Particulate Matter 1.0 (PM1.0), Particulate Matter 10 (PM10), Nitrogen Oxides (NOx), and Carbon Monoxide (CO). It shows that the IoT in the Amihan's Breath System consistently recorded the air pollutants and thermal environment.

Filtration Performance After Integrating the Filtration of the Amihan's Breath System Presented in this section is the filtration performance after integrating the filtration of the Amihan's Breath in terms of air pollutants.

Air Pollutants Concentration

To determine the filtration performance after integrating the filtration within the fourteen (14) days, the following formula was used by the researchers:

$$\text{Filtration Efficiency (\%)} = \frac{\text{Initial Concentration} - \text{Final Concentration}}{\text{Initial Concentration}} \times 100$$

Ozone (O3) Filtration Efficiency

$$\text{Ozone (O3)} = \frac{0.03 - 0.02}{0.03} \times 100 = 33.33\%$$

O3. A removal efficiency of 33.33% indicates that the filter successfully eliminated one-third of the ambient ozone passing through it. This efficiency is a critical metric calculated from the reduction of O3 concentration as the air passes through the filter. The initial O3 concentration was 0.03 ppm, while the final concentration after the filtration was 0.02 ppm. This means that the Amihan's Breath System is capable of lowering the Ozone (O3) of the indoor environment, although at a moderate efficiency.

Nitrogen Oxides (NOx) Filtration Efficiency

$$\text{Nitrogen Oxides (NOx)} = \frac{96.89 - 68.92}{96.89} \times 100 = 28.87\%$$

NOx. The initial concentration of NOx at 96.89 µg/m³ and a final, filtered, concentration of 68.92 µg/m³ having a filtration efficiency of 28.87%. This low efficiency strongly suggests that the filter is operating below ideal capacity because the number of activities is insufficient to effectively trap the NOx molecules. This means that the Amihan's Breath System is capable of lowering the Nitrogen Oxides (NOx) of the indoor environment, although at a moderate efficiency.

Particulate Matter 1.0 (PM1.0) Filtration Efficiency

$$\text{Particulate Matter 1.0 (PM1.0)} = \frac{18.08 - 4.77}{18.08} \times 100 = 73.62\%$$

PM1.0. Utilizing HEPA 13 filter component, demonstrated good efficiency against fine particulate matter, achieving a filtration efficiency of 73.62%. The filtration's strength in particle filtration confirms that it is highly effective and reliable lowers down fine particulate matter in the environment. This means that the Amihan's Breath System is capable of lowering the Particulate Matter 1.0 (PM1.0) of the indoor environment.

Particulate Matter 2.5 (PM2.5) Filtration Efficiency

$$\text{Particulate Matter 2.5 (PM2.5)} = \frac{30.31 - 6.07}{30.31} \times 100 = 79.97\%$$

PM2.5. The system reached an efficiency of 79.97%, showing its strong capability to clean the air by successfully reducing the PM2.5 concentration from an initial concentration 30.31 µg/m³ down to much cleaner 6.07 µg/m³. The high rate of removal is advantageous for improving air quality. The Amihan Breath System can therefore reduce the amount of PM2.5 found in the air within an interior location.

Particulate Matter 10 (PM10) Filtration Efficiency

$$\text{Particulate Matter 10 (PM10)} = \frac{85.64 - 8.24}{85.64} \times 100 = 90.38\%$$

PM10. The system's performance in removing particulate matter from the air is at an extremely high level, attaining an efficiency rating of 90.38%. This result shows that the Breath System removes PM10 from the air (reducing PM10 levels from 85.64 µg/m³ to an average of 8.24 µg/m³) with great effectiveness. The Breath System effectively captures and collects large particulate matter such as dust as well as many other airborne allergens that can cause allergic reactions in people. The Breath System is capable of substantially decreasing the PM10 levels in indoor environments.

Carbon Monoxide (CO) Filtration Efficiency

$$\text{Carbon Monoxide (CO)} = \frac{9.48 - 2.97}{9.48} \times 100 = 68.67\%$$

CO. The Amihan's Breath System achieved a strong and highly beneficial removal rate for CO, reaching an efficiency of 68.67%. Successfully reducing the initial concentration of 9.48 ppm to a cleaner 2.97 ppm. This result confirms that the system is effective in filtering the CO gas. This means the Amihan's Breath System is capable of lowering the Carbon Monoxide (CO) of the indoor environment.

Benzene Filtration Efficiency

$$\text{Benzene} = \frac{3.38 - 1.05}{3.38} \times 100 = 68.93\%$$

Benzene. Strong and effective filtration rate for the hazardous chemical, Volatile Organic Compound Benzene, reaching an efficiency of 68.93%. This performance. Successfully reducing the Benzene concentration from 3.38 ppb to a cleaner 1.05 ppb. This high score confirms that the

system's filtration is very effective against Benzene. This means the Amihan's Breath System is capable of lowering the benzene of the indoor environment.

Toluene and Xylene Filtration Efficiency

$$\text{Toluene} = \frac{14.97 - 5.19}{14.97} \times 100 = 65.33\%$$

$$\text{Xylene} = \frac{14.97 - 5.19}{14.97} \times 100 = 65.33\%$$

Toluene and Xylene. The filtration is strong and very effective in purifying harmful pollutants, specifically Toluene and Xylene. The system achieved a filtration efficiency of 65.33% for both. MICS5524 is used to detect the pollutants noting that this is a broadband sensor, which means it gives the same measurement for many pollutants, including Toluene and Xylene. This means the Amihan's Breath System is capable of lowering the benzene of the indoor environment.

Ammonia (NH₃) Filtration Efficiency

$$\text{Ammonia (NH}_3\text{)} = \frac{0.59 - 0.53}{0.59} \times 100 = 10.17\%$$

NH₃. Achieving a commendable efficiency of 10.17% for this specific basic gas, it successfully reduced the concentrations from 0.59 ppm to 0.53 ppm. This filtration rate is modest, it also means the Amihan's Breath System is capable of lowering the Ammonia (NH₃) of the indoor environment, although a moderate efficiency.

IV. DISCUSSION

The results of the Amihan's Breath System studies shows that it is highly reliable and effective in detecting and purifying the air, with a 97% to 99% success rate in crucial parameters required for detecting the air pollutants. The air pollutants sensor's reliable detection lets the system replace the filter automatically. In addition, the filtration's efficiency increases its reliability where the levels of the pollutants decrease as the filter is integrated. Minor problems arose when the researcher gathered data. Still, the researchers already expected that the prototype system would not meet the standard, since some of the prototype's sensors are low-cost sensors. Nonetheless, the data gathered after the integration of filtration showed that it lowered the threshold levels of before inside the dining room which indicates that the system is efficient. This finding is supported by the study Swamy (2021) and Christensen (2020) that the Amihan's Breath system is cost effective, filtration effective, and effective in monitoring and detecting indoor air pollutant parameters.

The Amihan's Breath System significantly improves monitoring indoor air quality and indoor air purification through key advancements. It features automated monitoring,

which ensures optimal indoor air quality without requiring manual intervention. The system also uses automatic filter replacement, which changes the used filter automatically depending on the activities, threshold level, and number of days it has been used. IoT integration enables continuous monitoring of air pollutants and thermal environment parameters, allowing for faster adjustments and better decision-making. This technology minimizes cost demands, allowing users to spend less than getting the two devices (airgradient, 2024 and Chen et al., 2023).

While the initial expenses may be higher, the long-term benefits of detecting, monitoring, and filtration making the system viable and cost-effective. Furthermore, the Philippines is exposed to both outdoor and indoor air pollution, with indoor exposure often driven by outdoor pollution entering closed spaces, plus local sources like cooking, biomass use, and ventilation practices. During high air pollution, residents face difficulties in detecting and purifying the air. Amihan's Breath will help in terms of keeping the indoor air quality in good threshold levels that is sensitive to the people like children from these kinds of inconvenience. The Amihan's Breath allows real-time time monitoring by detecting air pollutants and thermal environment transmitting data to the IoT. These results are in line with established findings that real-time, IoT-enabled air monitoring improves management of indoor environments (Davda, 2023). This is consistent with Adochiei et al. (2024) study that automated Indoor Air Quality monitoring is generally advantageous for indoor environments.

The findings also showed that the fourteen (14) days monitoring of proof-of-concept Amihan's Breath System were ranging 97% to 99% successful for all fourteen days. The air pollutants and thermal environment sensors was operating correctly, the notification was functioning correctly, the servo motor was acting properly, and the indoor air quality was maintained in suitable condition PM1.0: 10 µg/m³, PM2.5: 35 µg/m³, PM10: up to 150 µg/m³, NOx: up to 150 µg/m³, CO: 9 ppm, Ozone: 0.06 ppm, BTX compound, 0-10 ppb for benzene, 0-50 ppb for toluene and xylene, and 1.0 ppm. Clements et al. (2017) highlights low-cost sensors are crucial for expanding indoor air quality (IAQ) monitoring because they offer affordable and easy-to-use solutions, making real-time air pollution data.

V. CONCLUSIONS

Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusions are drawn by the researchers:

The Amihan's Breath system prototype successfully passed the functionality tests in terms of air pollutants and thermal environment sensor's detection, receiving data in IoT based on the data value the system gives, and system programming. The

system's monitoring capability proved exceptionally stable, pre-filtration tests established a high baseline (97% to 98%), which was further improved to a range of 99% to 100% after the filter integration, with six parameters reaching perfect 100% accuracy. This implies that the system can continuously monitor indoor air quality to detect pollutants and provide real-time data for a healthier environment.

The IoT-based notification in the Amihan's Breath system prototype achieved a 100% accuracy rate across the fourteen-day gathering data. By successfully avoiding False Negative (FN) instances and only recording True Positive (TP) and False Positive (FP) alerts, the system guarantees that users are never misled by a missed warning when pollutants threshold are exceeded.

The IoT in the Amihan's Breath system prototype was able to provide before and after integrating the filtration data on air pollutants and thermal environment. This indicates that residents can access current air pollutants and thermal environment data from any location using the IoT. This allows them to constantly check the indoor air quality without having to check it on the device.

The filtration efficiency of Amihan's Breath system in terms of air pollutants is exceptionally high, specifically particulate matter, successfully utilizing the HEPA 13 component to reduce fine and coarse particles (up to 90.38% for PM10). The system also shows strong and reliable removal rates for hazardous Volatile Organic Compound (VOCs) and Carbon Monoxide. While efficiencies for gases like Ozone and NOx are moderate, the system is fundamentally capable of lowering concentrations of indoor contaminants.

REFERENCES

1. ActionforBetterHealth.WorldHealthOrganization.<https://www.who.int/news/item/17-03-2025-nearly-50-million-people-sign-up-call-for-clean-air-action-for-better-health>
2. Adochiei, Pietraru, R. N., Olteanu, A., I., & Adochiei, F. (2024). Reengineering indoor air quality monitoring systems to improve End-User Experience. *Sensors*, 24(8), 2659. <https://doi.org/10.3390/s24082659>
3. AirGradient. (2024). Indoor Air Quality Monitor AirGradient ONE. AirGradient.
4. AQU Monitoring Services AQI.in. (2025). www.aqi.in; AQI Monitoring Services.
5. A Survey of Indoor Air Qualities studies in the Philippines (PDF) a survey of Indoor
6. Air Quality Studies in the Philippines. Available at: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/324824788_A_Survey_of_Indoor_Air_Quality_Studies_in_the_Philippines (Accessed: 05 November 2025).
7. Baeza-Romero, M. T., Dudzinska, M. R., Mehdi Amouei Torkmahalleh, Barros, N., Coggins, M. A., Duygu Gazioglu Ruzgar, Kildsgaard, I., Motahareh Naseri, Rong, L., Saffell, J., Ana Maria Scutaru, & Staszowska, A. (2022). A review of critical residential buildings parameters and activities when investigating indoor air quality and pollutants. 32(11). <https://doi.org/10.1111/ina.13144>
8. Chen, C., Pei, W., Ou, Q., & Pui, D. Y. H. (2023). Smart Filter Performance Monitoring System. *Aerosol and Air Quality Research*, 23(4), 220416. <https://doi.org/10.4209/aaqr.220416>
9. Clements, A. L., Griswold, W. G., RS, A., Johnston, J. E., Herting, M. M., Thorson, J., Collier-Oxandale, A., & Hannigan, M. (2017). Low-Cost Air Quality Monitoring Tools: From Research to Practice (A Workshop Summary). *Sensors*, 17(11), 2478. <https://doi.org/10.3390/s17112478>
10. DAO-2013-13-PM2.5.pdf - air quality management section. Available at: <https://air.emb.gov.ph/wp-content/uploads/2017/04/DAO-2013-13-PM2.5.pdf>
11. Dentr Administrative Order on establishing breakpoints for PM 2.5 Air Quality Index reviewed and approved by DENR (2020) Air Quality Management Section.
12. 425 DENR administrative order no. 2000 - 81 November 07, 2000 subject.
13. Du. (n.d.). https://du.lv/wp-content/uploads/2024/12/ABUD_2024_Raksts11.pdf
14. Estimating the Health & Economic Cost of air pollution in the Philippines. Centre for Research on Energy and Clean Air. (2023, February 6).
15. Estimating the Health & Economic Cost of Air Pollution in the Philippines. (n.d.).
16. Indoor Penetration of ambient particulate pollution Marciel, C., Tamayo, E. G., Babela, D. L., & Benjamin, P. (2022). Indoor penetration of ambient particulate pollution in a hospital maternity ward in Manila, Philippines: perspectives towards holistic city-level air quality management. *Environmental Science Atmospheres*.
17. Liu, J., He, C., Si, Y., Li, B., Wu, Q., Ni, J., Zhao, Y., Hu, Q., Du, S., Lu, Z., Jin, J., & Xu, C. (2024). Toward Better and Healthier Air Quality: Global PM2.5 and O3 Pollution Status and Risk Assessment Based on the New WHO Air Quality Guidelines for 2021. *Global Challenges*, 8(4). <https://doi.org/10.1002/gch2.202300258>
18. Liu, X., Jayaratne, R., Thai, P., Kuhn, T., Zing, I., Christensen, B., Lamont, R., Dunbabin, M., Zhu, S., Gao, J., Wainwright, D., Neale, D., Kan, R., Kirkwood, J., & Morawska, L. (2020). Low-cost sensors as an alternative for long-

- term air quality monitoring. Environmental Research, 185, 109438.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envres.2020.109438>
19. Swamy, G. (2021). Development of an indoor air purification system to improve ventilation and air quality. Heliyon, 7(10), e08153.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2021.e08153>
 20. World Health Organization. (n.d.). Nearly 50 million people sign up call for Clean Air Action for Better Health. World Health Organization.
 21. World (2024, October 16) Household air pollution 7 World. (2024, October 16).
 22. Household air pollution. Who.int; World Health Organization: WHO.